

Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 32 to 38

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The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19566>

Abstract

*This work bring different ways of representing prime magic squares. These are of types: **blocks, block-bordered, concentric, nested, etc.** This work is for the orders 32 to 38. For prime magic squares of orders 6 to 31 author's work [10, 11, 12, 13]. In case of prime magic squares of order 37, the compositions of order 35 are applied over 37 considering **single-layer borders** representing as **block-bordered prime magic squares**, with internal blocks based on different compositions of of prime magic squares of order 35. In case of orders 34 and 38, there is one block-wise composition in each case, i.e., of orders 17 and 19. In view of this, the some more alternatives are considered based on possibilities of orders 32 and 36.*

Keywords: magic squares, prime magic squares, block-wise magic squares, concentric magic squares, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

During past years, the author studied block-wise constructions of magic squares. The work for the magic square of orders 8 to 47. Below are few examples:

1.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** of order 8 is given by

8x8	pan	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
260	7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54	260	260
260	2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51	260	260
260	64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13	260	260
260	57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12	260	260
260	23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38	260	260
260	18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35	260	260
260	48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29	260	260
	41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28	260	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

It is composed four **equal sums pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

1.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 9

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 is given by

9x9 pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** (sum of only rows and columns) with equal magic sums.

Below is another example, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares, but the magic square of order 9 is not **pandiagonal**:

9 mgc										369
	31	36	29	76	81	74	13	18	11	369
	30	32	34	75	77	79	12	14	16	369
	35	28	33	80	73	78	17	10	15	369
	22	27	20	40	45	38	58	63	56	369
	21	23	25	39	41	43	57	59	61	369
	26	19	24	44	37	42	62	55	60	369
	67	72	65	4	9	2	49	54	47	369
	66	68	70	3	5	7	48	50	52	369
	71	64	69	8	1	6	53	46	51	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums.

1.3 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider a magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by

10x10	mgc											505
	91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505	
	13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88	505	
	89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12	505	
	11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90	505	
	96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5	505	
	1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100	505	
	93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8	505	
	7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94	505	
	95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6	505	
	9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505	
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

The blocks of order 8 are **equal sums** pandiagonal magic squares of order 10.

1.4 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as magic square of order 9 is given by

11x11	mgc											671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	21	38	43	55	60	68	80	85	99	1	671
	119	53	58	72	75	92	97	28	33	41	3	671
	117	82	87	95	26	31	45	48	65	70	5	671
	115	47	25	30	69	50	64	94	81	89	7	671
	11	67	54	62	101	79	84	42	23	37	111	671
	13	96	77	91	40	27	35	74	52	57	109	671
	15	34	39	29	59	73	51	90	98	76	107	671
	17	63	71	49	88	93	83	32	46	24	105	671
	19	86	100	78	36	44	22	61	66	56	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

The blocks of order 8 are **equal sums pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10.

1.5 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 12. First as magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. Second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

• Blocks of Order 3

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870
	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

• **Blocks of Order 4**

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870	
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870	
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870	
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870	
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870	
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870	
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870	
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870	
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870	
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870	
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870	
	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870	
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

• **Blocks of Order 6**

12	mgc													870
	1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870	
	138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870	
	132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870	
	18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870	
	7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870	
	139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870	
	55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870	
	84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870	
	78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870	
	72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870	
	61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870	
	85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870	
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

More on these kind of magic squares can be seen in author's work [29, 30, 31]. The aim of this work write magic squares with blocks of order 4 with distinct prime number entries.

Based on the idea of blocks, block-borders, etc. given above, we shall concentrate our work in this direction on **prime magic squares**. This whole work is given in many parts.

2 Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares of Orders 32 to 38

This work brings different ways representing magic squares in prime numbers. Initial aim is represent in terms of blocks. Some of possibilities led us to concentric or single-layer bordered magic squares. It includes blocks of orders 3, 4, 5, etc. Sometimes these blocks are of **equal** or **different** magic sums. This work is for the orders 32 to 38. For the previous orders refer authors work [10, 11, 12, 13]. Also there are two more works on prime magic squares recently done by the author. The first one is on **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic squares** of orders 120 and 121 [8]. The second one is **block-structured** prime magic squares of order 1220 multiples of 4 [9].

Whenever, we write **prime magic square**, it means that the magic squares are composed of **distinct prime number entries**, except in few cases, where the central constant 1000003 is repeating. It is considered only in case of odd order primes magic squares, where we need the equal sums magic squares.

This work is for the **prime magic squares** of orders 32 to 38. The table below give different representations for each order:

Order	Representations
32	07 (01-07)
33	07 (08-14)
34	09 (19-23)
35	05 (24-28)
36	15 (29-43)
37	05 (44-48)
38	14 (49-62)
Total	62

Example 38. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 9. *Let's consider following prime magic square of order 36*

776557	1001353	1064593	765613	804577	1336009	312553	1682809	1255963	1272247	1077289	1632307	321247	753547	1604497	1033567	605617	699709	280537	1096549	396709	970699	986437	844603	1520173	1232563	1671757	1456789	1557769	367027	1427347	562909	1602283	774073	556537	695293
--------	---------	---------	--------	--------	---------	--------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------	--------	--------	---------	---------	--------	--------	--------	---------	--------	--------	--------	--------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------	--------	---------	--------	---------	--------	--------	--------

It is block-structured prime magic square of order 36 composed of equal sums concentric prime magic squares of order 9.

3 Author's Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

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